

Gender Discrimination in Education in Northeast India with Special Reference to Assam: An Analysis

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Abstract: Assigning of gender role on the basis of sex is a common practice in our country, and this is perhaps the most prominent factor causing to the large scale gender inequality in India in particular. The differences and inequalities between sexes, however, are inevitable so far as the biological inheritance is concerned and this inequality between male and female does not affect in any way the respective growth and development of either sex. But the tendency to delineating men and women as such stratifying role assignment based on gender construct paves ways of unequal treatment to the sexes in terms of job preferences, right and privileges in all sectors of public and private work places. Needless to mention that men think themselves naturally superior to women and hence they deserve higher positions in society compared to their women fellow. A few of men in recent time, however, publicly advocate for women empowerment in different workplace including politics, employment, entrepreneurship etc. and they raise voices against discrimination on the basis of sex but that with little effect on society and even on themselves. This is because there is still an extreme level of gender inequality in India with a gender parity score of 0.84 compared to the ideal score of 1.00.

Key words: gender, discrimination, Education, Society, work place.

Introduction

The evils of gender inequality in India, however, has evolved as a system of social structure where men use to believe that they have the natural right to dominate, oppress and exploit women and as such it become a recognized rule that women should not come at par with men in respect of dignity and role playing. Barring a few exceptions, women have no power to take independent decisions, nor could they have the right to deal any transaction with bank. It is because men are supposed to be the custodian of women and women too seemingly accept and comply with this norm due to continued socio-cultural-religious conditioning.

The causes of discrimination against women in India are a little bit different from that of the western countries. The lower literacy rate of women, religious ideology, socio-economic and cultural bindings play crucial role in this respect. The roots of gender inequalities in our country however lie in the patriarchy system of our society. Poverty is still another factor of gender discrimination. Illiterate women get bound to work in low paying domestic works or work as street laborers at a lower rate compared to men for the same work.

Substantially the cases in economic affairs apart, education, health, leadership are some area where more than partially women get deprived of what they are likely to deserve. In almost every house hold, girl child receive less care and treatment of diseases than the boy child. Their education and employment issues are either ignored or put in the second preference. All domestic works like cooking, cleansing, washing; taking care of sibling and also of old parents and grandparents are solely left for the girl child. Wives are supposed to be the care taker of husbands, sisters are of the brothers, mothers are of fathers but never the cases seen in reverse.

Of late, there has emerged a so called liberalism in our society and the educated men seem to show respect to their wives by sharing cooking and washing occasionally for sake of doing their parts towards empowerment of women. But this is no more than a viewer's show. There are still numbers of cases found discriminating against women in respect of education, employment, health, freedom and choices, for example, girl child are enrolled in less costly schools, offered a different course preferably home science and less costly and easy courses. Similarly freedom of choice is denied to a girl child everywhere.

The causes of discrimination against women however lie not only in intent of men, many a time men exploit women lovingly at the unconscious level. They feel women to receive best treatment when they are treated subordinate to men.

Significance of the study:

Despite enormous studies have been carried out in this field till recently, the reality behind the drastic inequality between men and women could hardly been realized and this is probably because of the reason that a more generalized study based on random policy of data collection and a lesser emphasis on small and marginal units of population has been a common practice of all activists and research workers. The information thus accumulated reflects a generic discrimination scenario which could hardly represent the reality of the problem of particular sector of a region.

This study is significant for its intended specific focus on a small area with large variety interms of education, employment opportunities and privileges, freedom of expression, economic right, political involvement and decision making etc.

Objective of this study:

This paper intends to focus on issues and challenges of gender bias and sex discrimination prevalent in global society with special reference to Assam and North East. The intended aims and objective of this study consist of the following lines.

- 1) To highlight the existing discrimination scenario between man and women on the basis of sex.
- 2) To identify the causes responsible for growing pattern of gender discrimination.
- 3) To examine the effects of government's policy initiatives to curb the evils of gender discrimination.

Methodology:

This study is carried out on the basis of secondary data available with the department and concerned authority. Also consulted the documented papers, news item, and literary works of the researcher and the activists.

Findings:

This study takes into account the parameters of discrimination that have been found dominating the culture of the society commonly all across the world. The most common area of discrimination recorded in education and employment everywhere throughout the ages. Men are more likely to be literate on global average. But in some countries, predominantly the western countries like Latin America, North America and some eastern countries like, Japan, Russia female literacy is higher than that of male. In India and in North Eastern region in particular there exists state wise differences in literacy rate between men and women. According to census 2011 report, the sex ratio of Assam is 1000: 954 which is lower as compared to four other states of north east, i.e. Meghalaya, Manipur, Mizoram and Tripura. This difference of sex ratio reflects through the school enrolment of the children. The gross enrolment ratio (GER) of students from first grade to eighth grade across the state of Assam during the financial year 2020 was 107 percent. The enrolment ratio for male students was lower at 104 percent compared to female students at 110 percent that year.

According to All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) report 2017 -18 student enrolment at UG level has 51.9 percent male and 48.1 percent female. In Assam GER 18.2 percent in the year 2017-18 is extremely lower than the highest state level GER 56.4 percent achieved by Chandigarh. In Assam GER for male is 18.6 percent and for female is 17.8 percent. The highest male GER is 49.1 percent (Tamilnadu) and the highest female GER is 67.7 percent (Chandigarh). In Manipur the GER from 1st grade to 8th grade during financial year 2020 was 116 percent. The enrolment ratio for male students was higher at 114 percent than that of female at 117percent. In Meghalaya the GER of elementary education during that period was exceptionally high at almost 143 percent, of which male at 139 percent and female at 148 percent.

According to UDISE+ 2019-20 Ministry of education Government of India the enrolment ratio at elementary stage (1-8) are as follows-

State	Boys	Girls	Total
Assam	104.5	110.4	107.4
Meghalaya	143.4	147.8	143.5
Manipur	114.5	117.7	116.1
Mizoram	124.7	124.0	124.4
Nagaland	82.1	86.9	84.4
Arunachal Pradesh	103.5	106.9	105.2
Tripura	105.7	109.0	107.3

The above table depicting enrolment ratio of boys and girls however is not in critical position, but so far as the quality of education is concerned girls students have been put in back foot. The government and the donor agencies have focused primarily on increasing female access and enrolment with least attention to the quality and relevance of education for the girls or their achievement rates. In other words, to raise the enrolment rate of girl students at schools quality of their education is compromised. This is a hidden discrimination against girls students. According to Levine and others (2003) access, duration and quality are all critical variables in realizing educational benefits. Girls students are often treated as ‘‘dull and second rate students incapable of answering question.’’ Girls student have been discriminated by paying less attention to the gender dynamics and educational input. Several studies have revealed that girls student are less exposed to tough subjects and boys are assigned high status tasks. This contributes a lot in reinforcing the gender gap in education.

There are however multiple dimensions of gender discrimination in education. The frequently discussed areas of discrimination seem to constitute with the following five dimensions-

- (i) discrimination based on the social class
- (ii) discrimination on minority status
- (iii) discrimination on gender
- (iv) discrimination on institutional context
- (v) stereotype and discrimination.

(i) The working class children have less chances of succeeding in education. In primary stage however, the disparity between boys and girls has been brought to the minimum in recent time in respect of enrolment and retention, the discrimination still persists in higher education.

(ii) There is correlation between minority status and social class. The minority children achieve lower outcomes. They are often streamed into less challenging school tracks and they generally achieve lower educational degrees.

(iii) Unlike industrial countries, India and its states especially Assam witness gender gap in education against girl students in respect of enrolment and succeeding education. It is social class that affects educational attainment more for boys and men than for girls and women.

(iv) At the institutional level, the highest degree of discrimination is fostered by streaming students on the bases of their gender which seem instrumental to differentiate curriculum and instructional resources for boys and girls. The provision of streamed institution is likely to boost the disparity leading to growth of discriminating attitude among the boys and the men towards their opposite sex.

(v) Many time teachers biased judgment are affected by varieties of stereotype which lead to discrimination. The teachers seem to have lower expectations of minority children. They are also found to respond differently to immigrant children than the natives.

Besides, there seems multiple occasions/areas where discrimination towards girls and women has still been a common practice in the society across the globe. The workplace discrimination is one of the major areas where women suffer the most from this social evil. The prejudiced treatment in hiring and firing process on account of gender generally inclined towards the women. The women workers are waged less compared to male workers for the same work, they are subordinated to their male fellow and honored less in the staff, for e.g. women workers are called by their first name, they are held to follow the commandment of their male colleagues in the workplace or they often experience sexual harassment from their male companion.

Conclusion:

Gender discrimination however is not always held illegal and unjustified, there are instances of intended discrimination held no crime and the rule of laws does not allow litigation against such discriminative behavior against women especially in the workplace, for e.g. the office boss can't be held guilty of disregarding the subordinate staff, or discriminating the women workers in assigning with specific task which male workers do not fit for and vice versa. According to the Equality Act of UK 2010, there are nine protected characteristics against which litigation can be initiated by the victims of discrimination. In USA sex discrimination is explicitly outlawed under title vii of Civil Right Act 1964 prohibiting employment discrimination on account of race, color, religion, sex and national origin. In the light of the international laws on issues of discrimination, Indian government has enacted several laws prohibiting gender discrimination for e.g. the Equal Remuneration Act 1976, the Maternity Benefit Act, 1961, the NREGA 2005, the Dowry Prohibition Act 1961, the Immoral Traffic (prevention) Act etc. Besides, the enforcement of constitutional provisions envisaged in the articles 14, 15, 16, 39, 42 guaranty the equal rights of its citizens irrespective of sex, color, race and religion. But despite of these provisions there are still many instances of discrimination direct and indirect in multiplicity of different forms and types like disparate treatment, hiring and firing policy, pay disparity, sexual jokes, slurs and nonconsensual touch.

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